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Conference topic:

4. Politics and society in the Slavic countries

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Development of the State-Building Process and the Idea of Ukraine's Independence in the 19th – Early 20th Century

The relevance of this study is determined by the political crisis in Europe and the existence of numerous separatist movements. The issue of the development of Ukrainian state-building thought has gained particular significance in light of the ongoing state of war.

At the end of the 19th century, Ukrainians did not have their own state, and their ethnic lands were divided between Austria-Hungary and the Russian Empire.

In 1826, an investigation was conducted in Saint Petersburg regarding the "Malorussia Secret Society" aimed to separate Ukraine from Russia and unite it with Poland.

In 1845, the Slavic Society of St. Cyril and Methodius was founded in Kyiv, advocating for the creation of a federation of Slavic states.

In 1890, the Ukrainian Radical Party was established in Lviv, seeking Ukrainian autonomy.

In 1891, the "Brotherhood of Tarasovites" was founded in Kharkiv, promoting the autonomy of all nations within the Russian Empire.

In 1900, Mykola Mikhnovsky addressed the congress of the Revolutionary Ukrainian Party in Kharkiv with his speech "Independent Ukraine". However, the party itself did not adopt the idea of full independence.

During the revolutions of 1905 and 1917, a lot of revolutionary republics emerged in Ukraine.

On June 10, 1917, the Ukrainian Central Rada in Kyiv adopted the First Universal, declaring Ukraine's autonomy within Russia.

On April 29, 1918, a coup d'état led to the proclamation of the Ukrainian State, though without officially declaring independence.

On January 9, 1918, amid the Bolshevik-Ukrainian war, the Ukrainian Central Rada proclaimed Ukraine's independence.

On November 13, 1918, the government of the independent Western Ukrainian People's Republic was established.

The Ukrainian national movement gradually progressed toward independence, with political crises often acting as catalysts for state-building processes.